

**TECHNOLOGY TO INCREASE THE CREATIVE SKILLS OF THE
FUTURE LEADER**

Dono R. Babaeva

Professors, PhD

Tashkent State Pedagogical University

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Gulnara Kh. Jumasheva

PhD, Associate Professor

Nukus State Pedagogical University

Nukus, Karakalpakstan

Shaxida E. Oteniyazova

Lecturer

Nukus State Pedagogical University

Nukus, Karakalpakstan

Zuxra K. Naimova

Lecturer

Nukus State Pedagogical University

Nukus, Karakalpakstan

Palzada E. Oteniyazova

Lecturer

Nukus State Pedagogical University

Nukus, Karakalpakstan

Abstract: According to the experience of developed and highly developed countries, every nation has a worthy place in the world community with the ability to set great and promising goals and achieve them. Today, it is no exaggeration to say that Uzbekistan is at such a responsible crossroads in its history. Therefore, the Action Strategy, developed by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, is becoming an important and new national idea that will determine the fate of our future.

Key words: leader, creative, professional development, technology,
www.turkjphysiotherrehabil.org

Introduction

Today, in the development of developed countries, the technologicalization of the education system, the training of comprehensively mature personnel in line with modern development, adaptation to the processes of globalization are recognized as an urgent problem. In particular, the main and main goal of the higher education system is to train highly intellectual, creative, competitive professionals for professional activities. In the education system of the Republic, special attention is paid to improving the curriculum, content, standards, adaptation to the development of education in developed countries, in turn, improving the quality of training. Such changes necessitate the introduction of new technologies of learning, distance, project education, media education, education based on personal creativity.

The main results and findings

The state pays special attention to the development of preschool education.

In the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on measures to further improve the system of preschool education in 2017-2021; expansion of the network of preschool educational institutions, provision of qualified pedagogical staff, radical improvement of the level of preparation of children for school education, introduction of modern educational programs and technologies in the educational process, creation of conditions for comprehensive intellectual, moral, aesthetic, physical development of children attention was drawn. In the process of modern globalization and informatization of education, the creative qualities of the future educator are the requirements of the time, his personal abilities, natural and social potential are focused on the quality, effective organization of professional activity. Creative qualities of

future educators studying in the higher education system are one of the clear goals. creative approach to the organization, active in creating new, advanced, ideas that serve to develop students' learning activities, personal qualities, independent study of advanced pedagogical achievements and experiences, as well as constant, consistent exchange of ideas about pedagogical achievements with colleagues. brings Without exploring different forms of creativity, it is impossible to implement today without considering a set of approaches and attitudes to what and how to train a specialist based on principles. At the same time, the rapidly developing innovative educational system of the pedagogical structure of higher education should pay special attention to the problem of meeting the requirements of creative abilities, creative potential, self-creative development, creative individuality and creativity. Radical reform of the education system, the formation of a harmoniously developed generation has become one of the most pressing issues determining our future.

The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev dated September 9, 2017 "On measures to radically improve preschool education" reads: The existing systemic shortcomings, such as the inability to provide qualified specialists, hinder the full implementation of public policy in the field of preschool education.

In order to be a teacher, to cultivate the intellect of others, to enjoy enlightenment, to cultivate a true patriot, a true citizen, first of all, the educator must meet such high requirements and have such great qualities. It will be difficult to bring up a harmoniously developed generation with a high level of knowledge and spirituality in the future if we do not attract teachers who know their job well, are qualified and have the creative potential to approach each child individually, and form their consciousness and thinking from childhood. said the head of our state Sh.M. Mirziyoyev.

Another factor in the successful solution of these tasks is the awareness of the staff of the system of continuing education, teachers and teachers of the

essence of modern educational technologies and their effective use in the educational process, as well as a creative approach to the organization of the educational process.

The ability of future educators to creatively organize the process of teaching the basics of private sciences in non-traditional forms, to design the educational process on the basis of perfect standards, to use these projects rationally. can be a guarantee. In recent years, special attention has been paid to improving the system of preschool education, updating the content, form, means and methods of education. Preschool education creates the necessary organizational, methodological, psychological, pedagogical conditions for the upbringing of healthy, comprehensively mature children. One of the most important directions in the educational process in preschool education is the use of advanced pedagogical and information technologies, filling organizations with educators with modern knowledge and professionalism, a sense of creative approach to work.

"Increasing and improving the capacity of teachers in the education system", the need to increase the creative knowledge and capacity of future teachers - educators. The concept of "creativity" can be interpreted as follows: Creativity - a creative ability that characterizes the readiness of the individual to produce new ideas and is part of the talent as an independent factor. The essence of the concepts of "creativity" and "pedagogical creativity". It has not been long since the concept of "creative pedagogy" began to be used in modern pedagogy. However, there is a need to decide on innovative and creative approaches to the teaching process. He ensured the formation of "creative pedagogy" as an independent subject among the pedagogical disciplines. The formation and development of a creative person depends on the interaction of changes in his inner and outer world, socio-economic conditions and the content of activities that require continuity, succession from birth to the end of life. The formation of a creative personality can be defined as the development of an individual in the

creation of mutually compatible creative activity and creative products. The speed and scope of this process depends on biological and social factors, the activity and creative qualities of the individual, as well as the existing conditions, vital and professionally conditioned events.

Pedagogical creativity is the ability of a teacher to create new ideas that serve to ensure the effectiveness of the educational process, as opposed to traditional pedagogical thinking, as well as to describe the readiness to positively address existing pedagogical problems. According to E.P. Torrens, "creativity" is the advancement of a problem or scientific hypothesis; - check and change the hypothesis; - identify the problem based on the formation of the decision; - Sensitivity to the contradictions between knowledge and practical actions in finding a solution to a problem Creative thinking can be clearly reflected in any social sphere. The creativity of a teacher is reflected in his creative approach to the organization of professional activities. In recent years, this situation is characterized by the concept of "pedagogical creativity." "Creative pedagogy" should guarantee the following two conditions: 1) to attract the attention of students to the basics of science by teachers who have a low level of mastery of academic subjects and find it boring to study them; 2) create opportunities for teachers to use them effectively in the classroom by recommending strategies and tools that encourage students to think creatively and creatively.

In modern conditions, it is necessary for a teacher to have creative qualities. In recent years, in the education system of leading foreign countries, special attention is paid to the formation of creative qualities in students and pupils. Literature on the formation and development of skills and abilities of teachers to take a creative approach to pedagogical activity is published.

Every year, the governing bodies of the education system focus on achieving high efficiency in educational institutions. For this purpose, a

curriculum will be developed, new textbooks will be created. This will help both students and teachers grow professionally.

The practical actions taken create a certain level of need for students to achieve success, to move forward, to help them develop their learning skills to some extent. However, at the end of the academic year, there is no high level of positive results in the study of subjects by students in higher education institutions. Many students have lost interest in learning. As a result, teachers are no longer thinking about organizing professional activities with the same enthusiasm as before.

Although new measures have been taken by the education authorities to change the activities of teachers who are reluctant to teach such students, the situation remains unchanged. What is the reason for this? perhaps it is not interesting for the students to think and plan the lessons in advance, but the fact that the content of the education is in a certain pattern does not give any incentive to the students.

Rejection of pre-planning of lessons, formation and development of critical, creative thinking in students, forcing them to think creatively, to come up with new ideas will change the attitude to education, will be a key factor in motivating them to succeed. In order to fully understand the general essence of the process of developing the qualities of creativity in a person, it is first necessary to understand the meaning of the concept of "creativity". According to Ken Robinson, "creativity is a set of original ideas with their own value" (Azzam, 2009).

Gardner, on the other hand, explains the concept in his research: "Creativity is a practical action performed by an individual, which must reflect a certain innovation and have a certain practical value." Many studies have differing views on the relationship between intelligence and creativity. While one group of researchers argues that there is no correlation between them, representatives of the second group point out that the level of creativity and

intelligence are interrelated (Kim, 2005). The concept of “creativity” reflects cultural diversity.

For Westerners, creativity is a novelty in general. They focus on creativity, non-traditionalism, curiosity, imagination, a sense of humor and freedom.

Although Western and Eastern views on creativity are different, representatives of both cultures value this quality and its ownership. Comprehensive thinking requires students to rely on many ideas in the performance of their assignments, problems, and tasks. In contrast, one-sided thinking is based on a single correct idea. There is no denying one-sided and multi-faceted thinking on the issue in observation. Consequently, all-round thinking is equally important in shaping creativity. That is, to complete the task, the student seeks several options for solving the problem (multi-faceted thinking), and then stops at a single correct solution that guarantees the most optimal result (one-sided thinking).

A person's creativity is manifested in his thinking, communication, emotions, certain types of activities. Creativity describes a person as a whole or its specific characteristics. Creativity is also reflected as an important factor of talent. In addition, creativity determines the sharpness of the mind, "ensures the active involvement of students in the educational process." In foreign countries, teachers, like specialists in all fields, determine the presence and level of their creative qualities. The answers to the questions suggested by the student should satisfy these four criteria. According to E.P. Torrens, the concept of "creativity" is based on the following: - To advance the problem or scientific hypotheses;

- check and change the hypothesis;

- identify the problem based on the formation of the decision;

- sensitivity to the contradictions of knowledge and practical actions in finding solutions to problems.

Conclusion

Creative thinking can be clearly reflected in every social area. The creativity of a teacher is reflected in his creative approach to the organization of professional activities. In recent years, this situation is characterized by the concept of "pedagogical creativity." Pedagogical creativity is the ability of a teacher to create new ideas that serve to ensure the effectiveness of the educational process, as opposed to traditional pedagogical thinking, as well as to describe the readiness to positively address existing pedagogical problems.

"Creative pedagogy" should be able to guarantee the following two conditions:

1) to attract the attention of students to the basics of science, who have a low level of mastery of academic subjects by teachers and find it boring to study them;

2) to enable teachers to use them effectively in the classroom by recommending strategies and tools that encourage students to think creatively and creatively. Due to the educator's lack of creative qualities, students also have interesting and brilliant ideas, but are prone to delays in expressing them. For this reason, the methods used in the educational process are determined by the fact that they do not serve to develop students' free, independent thinking skills. The tools and strategies recommended by the author are useful for teachers in the development of creativity in students and develop students' interest, aspiration to study academic subjects.

References

1. Mirziyoev Sh.M. Meeting on "Capacity building and improvement of teaching staff in the education system." –T .: 2018y.

2. Mirziyoev Sh.M. Resolution "On measures to radically improve preschool education." –T .: 2017 y.

3. Mirziyoev Sh.M. We will resolutely continue our national development path and take it to a new level.– T .: NMIU "Uzbekistan", 2017.

4. Yarmatov R. Nurturing and developing the personality of the future teacher. - T .: "Science and Technology" Publishing House, 2009.
5. Zufarov Sh. Pedagogical innovation. - T .: "Science and Technology" Publishing House, 2012.
6. Rasulov A. Geocological aspects of sustainable development // V International Scientific and Practical Conference .. Penza, 2020. Science and Education Penza. 307-310 p.
7. Rasulov A., Rasulova N. Methodology of geocological indicators of sustainable development, global geocological indicators // Modern scientific research: topical issues, achievements and innovations collection of articles of the XIII International Scientific and Practical Conference. Penza, 2020. 302-305 p.
8. Nigmatov A.N., Abdireimov S.J., Rasulov A., Bekaeva M.E. Experience of using gis technology in the development of geocological maps // International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology 13. № 12. 4835-4838 p.
9. Djamilova N.N. On the question of the formation of organizational qualities in preschoolers (research materials) // Pedagogical sciences, no. 2, pp. 11-15.
10. Djamilova N.N. Features of organizing steam education in Uzbekistan // Solid State Technology Volume: 63 Issue, 2020. 1083-1087 p.
11. Djamilova N.N. Formation of professionally significant qualities in future educators of preschool institutions // Public education. Tashkent, 2007, issue 5.18-146 p.